

Horner Syndrome Secondary to Otitis in A 9-Month-Old Persian Cat

Dr. Lees Tresa Louis¹, Dr. Litty Elizabeth Louis²

¹Undergraduate Scholar, College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Pookode, Wayanad

²Undergraduate Scholar, College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Pookode, Wayanad

Abstract

Horner's syndrome is a neurological disorder caused by the dysfunction of the oculosympathetic pathway. This case report discusses Horner syndrome in a 9-month-old Persian cat, presenting with signs of eye discharge, anisocoria, third eyelid prolapse, and blackish ear discharge. The diagnosis was confirmed through clinical examination, noting characteristic features of Horner syndrome, and otodectic ear mites were identified. Treatment with antibiotics and ear-cleansing agents resolved the condition over a two-week period. This report highlights the link between otitis and Horner syndrome, underscoring the importance of accurate diagnosis and prompt treatment.

Introduction:

Horner syndrome is a neurological disorder caused by a disruption in the sympathetic nerve supply to the eye and facial muscles. Common causes include ear infections, trauma,

and idiopathic conditions. The condition usually occurs suddenly and typically affects one side of the head. In felines, especially Persian cats prone to ear issues, otitis can predispose them to secondary conditions like Horner syndrome. This report details a case of Horner syndrome in a Persian cat following otitis.

History:

A 9-month-old golden-coloured female Persian cat weighing 1.4 kg was presented at DVC Ernakulam on 24 March 2024. The owner reported that the cat is persistently closing its right eye, had discharge from both eyes for one week, and showed signs of ear discomfort. The cat was hyporectic and otherwise healthy, with

no normal urination or defecation. The cat had not been vaccinated or dewormed and had a history of otitis. It had been previously treated with Calm ear drops, but the problem was not resolved.

Clinical Signs:

Upon examination, clinical parameters (respiration, pulse, and heart rate) were normal, but the mucous membranes were slightly congested, and the cat had a fever of 104.1°F. Mild lymph node enlargement was noted. Observations included right-sided ptosis, anisocoria, prolapse of the third eyelid, and dark

blackish discharge from both ears. These symptoms were consistent with Horner

syndrome, particularly the presence of ptosis, miosis, and third eyelid prolapse.

Diagnosis:

Samples from the ear discharge were collected, and examination revealed the presence of ear mites (*Otodectes cynotis*), known to cause otitis externa and possibly trigger neurological sequelae like Horner syndrome. Clinical signs—miosis, ptosis, third eyelid prolapse, and enophthalmos—confirmed the diagnosis of Horner syndrome secondary to otitis.

Treatment:

The treatment plan included antibiotic injections to control infection and anti-inflammatory agents to reduce nerve inflammation. The animal was administered with Inj Enrofloxacin @5mg/kg s/c and Inj Meloxicam @0.2 mg/kg s/c. Additionally, Ambiflush ear cleanser was prescribed for regular cleaning, while Pomisol ear drops were advised for ear instillation and selamectin spot on was also administered.

After two weeks, a follow-up examination revealed a complete recovery with resolution of Horner syndrome signs, and the ear discharge was no longer present.

Discussion

Horner syndrome in cats can arise from a variety of causes, with otitis being a notable factor in predisposed breeds like the Persian. Prompt identification and treatment of the underlying otitis and associated symptoms can lead to a full

recovery, as illustrated by this case. This report emphasizes the role of thorough clinical evaluation and targeted treatment in

After 14 days

managing Horner syndrome secondary to ear infections. In many cases, once the underlying ear infection is treated, improvement in Horner's syndrome symptoms can be seen within a few weeks to a couple of months.

References

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